

PART I

RED • GREEN • YELLOW

Personality
vs.
Type of Diet

Health-Promoting
Action of Phytochemicals

ALEKSANDRA DROZD-RZOSKA

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PERSONALITY VS. TYPE OF DIET

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Prakriti is a fundamental concept in Ayurveda and provides a basis for personalised healthcare. It refers to an individual's constitutional type and is used to guide recommendations related to diet, lifestyle, prevention, and therapy. Traditionally, the assessment of *Prakriti* has relied mainly on the practitioner's clinical experience and subjective judgment.

However, *Prakriti* is not understood merely as a fixed characteristic, but rather as a dynamic framework for explaining how an individual maintains health and balance (*Svasthya*) in interaction with the surrounding environment.

Prakriti is closely associated with the relative dominance of the three *Doshas*: *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*. These *Doshas* influence physical, physiological, and psychological traits, while their predominance may shape an individual's susceptibility to particular diseases. Traditionally, *Vata*-dominant individuals are considered more prone to disorders such as arthritis or insomnia, *Pitta*-dominant individuals to inflammatory conditions such as ulcers, and *Kapha*-dominant individuals to obesity or respiratory problems. Therefore, understanding the dietary principles appropriate for a given *Dosha* may support preventive health strategies by helping individuals avoid aggravating factors and adopt balancing practices [1].

Rooted in the philosophy of Ayurveda¹:

"Ayurveda defines health as a state of balance among the doshas, bodily tissues (Dhatus), waste products (Malas), and mental faculties, with Prakriti serving as the baseline for this balance."

"By aligning lifestyle, diet, and therapies with one's Prakriti, individuals can prevent Dosha imbalances (Vikriti), which are the root cause of disease in Ayurveda."

¹ Kumar, A., Balahia, G., Chambyal, K., & Thamman, R. K. (2025). Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Sciences, 10(9), p. 134. <https://doi.org/10.21760/jaims.10.9.20> Photo source: pexels.com

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PERSONALITY VS. TYPE OF DIET

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INTRODUCTION

Among the many concepts of Ayurveda, *Trayaupsthambha* — the three pillars of healthy and harmonious life, namely *Ahara* (diet and nutrition), *Nidra* (sleep), and *Brahmacharya* (proper management of vital energy and self-discipline) — holds a particularly important place, as Ayurveda regards longevity, well-being, and happiness as being based on these three foundations [2]. Swapnali Yewale and Prasad Yewale also underline the central role of food in Ayurveda, stating that²:

*“Ahara gives the body strength, radiance, and Ojas;
it is essential for longevity and enhances the strength of the mind.”*

According to Ayurvedic philosophy, maintaining health is based first of all upon the quality of food and on an understanding of the characteristics of one’s own body, while food should be treated with respect, and meals should be a feast for the senses, the soul, and the body [3, 4]. Moreover, Ayurvedic thought has long emphasized that food should not be treated merely as a source of calories, but as a factor supporting health, balance, vitality, and harmony between the body and mind. Food quality, freshness, colour, taste, aroma, method of preparation, season, and individual constitution are all important factors in dietary choice [3, 4].

Compared with the Ayurvedic approach to diet and nutrition, contemporary dietary studies tend to focus more on verifying eating habits, calculating caloric intake and portion weights, and formulating specific dietary recommendations, while individual lifestyle is not always fully considered [5]. Moreover, modern diets do not necessarily avoid processed foods, including products containing preservatives used to extend shelf life.

Dietetics, as the science of rational nutrition, combines knowledge from many disciplines: food technology, biochemistry, physiology, pathophysiology, clinical medicine, and hygiene. Ongoing studies enable verification of dietary/nutrition habits, the introduction of specific recommendations and diets, and the integration of these with lifestyle. They also indicate the consequences of inappropriate nutrition. Numerous books have been published that present the latest trends in nutrition and popularise diets, such as the Montignac diet, the Mediterranean diet, Dr. Kwaśniewski’s diet, the Atkins diet, the South Beach diet, the Copenhagen diet, the cabbage diet, the vegetarian diet, and the Cambridge diet. Each diet recommends and/or excludes specific food products and requires strict adherence to its recommendations and avoidance of its contraindications. The effectiveness of those diets is the subject of much controversy; often, the harmful consequences of their application call for careful thought and analysis of one’s own organism’s needs. It is often the case that the diet

² Yewale, S., & Yewale, P. (2023). International Journal of Life Science and Pharma Research, 13(6), L205–L210, p.1
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imposes lifestyle, rather than being adjusted to the needs and requirements of the given organism. This is connected with being determined to reach one's goal, which is not necessarily advantageous for one's own health [5].

However, contemporary preservation technologies, particularly high-pressure processing (HPP), offer an innovative, health-oriented approach to food production and preservation, with important implications for nutrition, by making it possible to extend the shelf life of food while helping to preserve its nutritional value, sensory qualities, colour, taste, and freshness [6, 7, 8].

In the case of fruit and vegetables, the preservation of natural colour and bioactive compounds is particularly important, as these features are closely related to their sensory attractiveness and potential health-promoting value [7, 9, 10, 11]. In this sense, HPP may be seen as a modern technological approach that supports the availability of fresh-like, colourful, and nutritionally valuable plant-based foods, thereby bringing contemporary food technology closer to the broader idea of health-supporting nutrition [6, 7, 8].

Modern food science seems to confirm this holistic perspective in contemporary scientific language. New preservation technologies, including high-pressure processing (HPP), extend the shelf life of food while preserving its natural colour, fresh taste, sensory appeal, and nutritional value [6, 7, 8, 12, 13]. This is especially important for plant-based foods, whose colour is often associated with bioactive compounds such as carotenoids, anthocyanins, chlorophylls, flavonoids, and other phytochemicals [9, 10, 11, 14, 15].

Therefore, modern food preservation methods may be understood as a technological response to an old nutritional idea: food should remain as close as possible to its natural, health-supporting quality. By preserving colour, taste, freshness, and valuable nutrients, contemporary food technologies can support the creation of food that not only satisfies hunger but also promotes well-being [6, 7, 8, 12, 13].

The aim of this contribution is to introduce a relatively little-recognised Ayurvedic approach to nutrition and to discuss it in the context of contemporary food production methods designed to preserve food's sensory and nutritional attributes. The relationships between nutrition, lifestyle, individual constitution, appearance, well-being, and health predispositions are particularly interesting, both from the perspective of self-knowledge and from the practical need to identify, among the wide range of available foods, those that are most suitable for maintaining well-being, appearance, and psycho-physical balance [3, 4].

In particular, the point is to describe and discuss the three types of personality/colours: yellow, red, and green, as well as the phytochemicals closely related to them. The colour of the food product should indicate whether it is suitable for a given organism. Contemporary nutritional science also indicates that the colour of plant foods is often associated with specific pigments and bioactive compounds, including carotenoids, anthocyanins, chlorophylls, betalains, and flavonoids [9, 10, 11, 14, 15].

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I. AYURVEDA – ‘THE KNOWLEDGE OF LIFE’

Ayurveda, often referred to as the ‘mother of medicine’, is one of the oldest medical knowledge systems, with roots dating back between 4,000 and 6,000 BCE. Ayurveda is part of the *Vedas*, the oldest set of writings of human civilization. The knowledge contained in the *Vedas* [literally: knowledge] existed as an oral tradition for at least a few thousand years before it was written down in the ancient language of India – *Sanskrit* [3, 4, 16].

Writing down the *Vedas* resulted not only in the spreading of the principles of Ayurveda but also in the introduction of numerous modifications by sages. There are three fundamental texts/treatises, referred to as *Samhitas*, making up the collection of Ayurveda wisdom:

- ☯ *Charaka Samhita* – which presents the main concepts, diseases, and cures for them,
- ☯ *Sushruta Samhita* – which discusses anatomy and surgery,
- ☯ *Astanga Hridaya* – which contains an overview of the studies of Charaka and Sushruta, as well as those of other known doctors and teachers of Ayurveda.

Ayurveda has two complementary aims: to maintain the health of those who are healthy, and to treat those who are ill.

Ayurveda represents a holistic approach to the human organism and provides the necessary knowledge for taking care of one’s health: how to be happy and how to achieve balance between the body and the mind. It distinguishes eight specialized branches of medicine, provides information on diagnostic procedures and treatment and therapy techniques, teaches the principles of ethical treatment, outlines the features of a good doctor, and even provides guidance on building hospitals [3, 4, 16].

I.1 THE CONCEPT OF THREE GUNAS

Following the philosophy of Ayurveda, in every situation the organism is subject to the influence of three natural impulses (known as *Gunas*), defined as ‘mental *Doshas*’, namely: *Tamas Guna* – the force of confusion, darkness, inertia, which causes withdrawal; *Rajas Guna* – the force of energy and movement, which determines the direction of action; as well as *Sattva Guna* – the force of balance, which is characterised by striving towards development and clarity of purpose. Because *Tamas* causes neglect, erroneous perception, and idleness, and dulls consciousness. *Rajas* promotes vanity, egocentric ambitions, distortions, and a sense of abomination, while *Sattva* contributes to an enhanced inclination towards virtue and knowledge as goals in themselves; we have to continuously work on our *Gunas*, or tendencies [3, 4, 16].

The concept of the three *Gunas*, specific to Ayurveda, allows for the recognition of human mental constitution and spiritual predispositions. It is assumed that the *Gunas* are perceived as specific, controlling the forces of nature, exerting equal influence upon an individual human organism and the world, and are widely understood. Their influence upon

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the world is manifested by the five basic elements, having in them both the material and energy aspects: ether – originating from *Sattva Guna*; air – from *Sattva* and *Rajas*; fire – from *Rajas Guna*; water – from *Rajas* and *Tamas* and earth – from *Tamas Guna* [3, 4, 16].

Those elements refer to the ‘true soil’, water, fire, air, space (ether), but are abstract.

I.2 THE CONCEPT OF THREE *DOSHAS*

Ayurveda is based upon the assumption that energy is manifested in everything that exists; in Sanskrit, the energy is called *Prana*. In man, *Prana* is present in the form of three differentiated biological energies – *Doshas*, which are the active reflections of the five elements. Specific *Doshas* that determine the psycho-physical constitution emerge from the dominant and unique combination of two elements. In the case of domination of ether and air, we have the *Vata* type; when fire and water dominate, we have the *Pitta* type; whereas the *Kapha* type is related to the energy of water and soil (earth) [1, 3, 4, 17].

Doshas control all the biological and psychic functions of the body, spirit, and consciousness; they guide our primeval preferences for taste, smell, foodstuffs, climatic conditions, heat, and cold; they also motivate us for specific types of behaviour. *Vata* in the human organism is connected with breathing, circulation, and thinking. At the emotional level, it is responsible for both positive emotions, such as creativity or flexibility, and negative ones, such as fear or anxiety. *Pitta* controls metabolism, temperature, sight, and mental efficiency. It is responsible for the sensation of hunger and thirst, as well as for the digestion of food. At the emotional level, it is connected with courage, ambition, anger, and pride. *Kapha* influences moisture, binding, and structure. It is held responsible for ligaments, bones, fluids, muscles, etc. At the emotional level, it is responsible for both love and devotion and for greed and envy [1, 3, 17].

Each man is born with a unique genetic code, or inborn psycho-physical constitutions, called *Prakriti* in Sanskrit. That specific combination of the three *Doshas*, in opposition to the *Gunas*, remains unchanged throughout one’s lifetime, although it may change due to severe chronic disease. Also, lifestyle, diet, emotions, and activities we engage in can increase specific *Doshas*, leading to a loss of balance [1, 3, 17].

Ayurvedic practices aim to restore the harmony of the *Doshas*. However, the simplest way of keeping the balance is not to allow our constitution to become imbalanced. For that purpose, it is necessary to define one’s own type of constitution, that is, to recognize one’s strengths and weaknesses, psychic and emotional predispositions; to define the correct diet, and, in case of a disease, to take up the individually selected methods and manners of treatment [1, 3, 4, 16, 17].

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II. THE INFLUENCE OF FOOD ON HEALTH

A condition for the proper functioning of the body is to provide it continuously with suitable nutrients in the right combination, in the right amounts, and of suitable quality. The quality of the foodstuffs we consume determines our existence, influences our attitude, and shapes our relationship with our surroundings. To maintain proper metabolic processes, we need to consume food and a specific amount of water, which facilitates the transport of nutrients to all cells of the organism and enables the excretion of unwanted metabolic products. Food should also contain dietary fibers, as they increase the volume of the food, support the motility of the alimentary tract, and perform specific functions in metabolism. Nutrients that the organism can produce itself using other compounds are called endogenous ones, whereas those that the body absolutely has to obtain from food are called exogenous ones. Proper nutrition should meet the body's quantitative and qualitative energy requirements; it should also provide nutrients that ensure compliance with the three basic requirements the body must meet: energy provision, construction, and regulation [5, 11, 18].

At present, there are numerous evidence indicating that both excessive and insufficient nutrition disturbs the correct physical and mental condition, reduces the immunity of human organism, and is the cause of the majority of contemporary civilization-related diseases, which include: obesity, diseases of the cardiovascular system, diabetes mellitus, non-neoplastic diseases of the large intestine, gallstone disease, dental caries, osteoporosis, neoplasms, and others [5, 6, 19, 20].

Maintaining proper life processes requires supplying the body with sufficient water and about 60 essential nutrients daily:

- ✘ 10 exogenous amino-acids, being ingredients of full standard proteins;
- ✘ 2-5 indispensable polyunsaturated fatty acids – linoleic acid, α -linolenic acid and their derivatives (arachidonic, eicosapentaenoic, and docosahexaenoic acids)
- ✘ 1-3 saccharides (glucose, fructose, galactose)
- ✘ 21 mineral components, i.e., macroelements (calcium, phosphorus, iron, iodine, magnesium, potassium, sodium, chlorine, sulfur) and microelements (zinc, copper, manganese, cobalt, molybdenum, selenium, fluorine, chromium, nickel, silicon, titanium, vanadium),
- ✘ 18 vitamins and compounds having the properties of vitamins (vitamin A, D, E, K, C, B₁, B₂, B₆, B₁₂, H, PP, folic acid, pantothenic acid, para-aminobenzoic acid, lipoic acid, choline, inositol, rutin), → facilitates the transport
- ✘ water, an essential component of every cell of the body, facilitates the transport of nutrients to all cells of the body, and enables the excretion of the unwanted products of metabolism.

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When discussing the importance of nutrients in the human diet, one should note that the brain can signal whether we are satiated. That control is manifested in three spatial dimensions: short-term control – satiety may be supported by foods rich in fibre and pectin; apples, potatoes, rice, flour-based processed products; long-term control – whether we want to eat or not is decided by the level of glucose in the blood, which flows through the hypothalamus, where there are the centres which control thirst and hunger; multi-year control – intake of food depends upon a complicated system of neuro-hormonal interactions [5].

The food eaten daily undergoes numerous transformations before its nutrients are absorbed and begin to perform their functions in the body.

During digestion, nutrients in the food undergo numerous mechanical and chemical processes. Compounds with simpler structures thus originate and are then absorbed by the organism, and, in solution, permeate the blood and lymph. Nutrients assimilated by the body then undergo metabolic processes characteristic of a given organism.

Besides nutrients, food products also contain indigestible ingredients. They fill the intestines, stimulating them for movements, and become part of the faeces. From the point of view of classical medicine, digestion of food begins in the oral cavity. Then the food is digested in the stomach and the duodenum. The final processes of digestion take place in the small intestine, while in the large intestine water is absorbed and faeces are formed [5].

Ayurvedic medicine considers improper digestion the main factor in the disease process. Digestion of food begins in the mouth, where tasting and chewing occur. Salivary glands provide moisture and enzymes to begin the initial preparation of food for digestion. These processes are possible thanks to the activity of the *sub-Dosha Prana Vata*, which enables us to see, hear, smell, and taste. However, the sensation of taste is possible thanks to the *sub-Dosha Bodhaka Kapha* located in the tongue. The reception of various tastes helps protect the organism against health problems, mainly related to *Kapha* [21, 22, 23].

Ayurveda recommends slow, very thorough chewing of food so that a perfectly ground mass of food reaches the stomach. The digestion of food in the stomach (*Jathara*) is called fire (*Agni*). The fire of the stomach heats the food, and with the assistance of the *sub-Dosha Pachaka Pitta* located in the stomach and the small intestine, produces a nourishing fluid called *Ahara Rasa*, which is then transported to the tissues. The fire of the stomach feeds and forms seven tissues: lymph, blood, and the muscular, fatty, osseous, generative, nervous, and bone marrow tissues [21, 22].

Pitta is the main *Dosha* associated with digestion, as it is responsible for generating the proper amount of heat, energy, and acidity, and for the food-processing processes that take place with the participation of the stomach and liver. The part of the food that contains no nutrients reaches the large intestine. This waste product of metabolism (*Mala*) is transported by the *sub-Dosha Apana Vata*, located in the large intestine and the lower part of the abdomen, and is then excreted through the rectum [21, 22, 24].

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The eighth, most subtle tissue, strongly related to the quality and kind of food being eaten, is called *Ojas*. Its optimal level supports the organism's immunity, determination, and enthusiasm for life. The importance of nutrition in Ayurvedic practice is sometimes illustrated by comparing severe *Ojas* insufficiency to profound immune-deficiency states; however, such comparisons should be understood symbolically rather than as a direct biomedical equivalence. When selecting a diet, one should first of all take into consideration the strength of the stomach fire, the so-called *Jatharagni* [21, 22, 24, 58].

III. PHYTOCOMPOUNDS VS. *DOSHAS*

In Ayurveda, the digestion of food in the stomach is one of the most crucial principles, alongside the concept of the *Doshas*. The daily (*circadian*) rhythm of *Agni* manifests as the alternating sensations of hunger and appetite. Disturbance of this cycle leads to an overlap between appetite and food digestion, causing disruptions in the body's functioning. Four conditions of *Agni* are distinguished in which *Agni* may function [3, 25, 58]:

Vishamagni – applies to people with a *Vata* constitution, or others, when *Vata* is aggravated,
Symptoms: constipation, flatulence, diarrhea, flatulent colics, borborygmus.

Mandagni – applies to people with a *Kapha* constitution, or others, when *Kapha* is aggravated
Symptoms: nausea, heaviness, cough, coated tongue, excessive production of saliva.

Samagni – the condition of the three *Doshas* being balanced.
Symptoms: food is digested efficiently, nutrients reach every organ, and waste products are excreted without leaving toxic residues.

Tikshnagni – applies to people with a *Pitta* constitution, or others, when *Pitta* is aggravated,
Symptoms: xerostomia, heartburn, excessive thirst.

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It is crucial to diagnose symptoms indicating derangement of digestive processes and to take appropriate action to harmonize them. *Agni* should not be self-regulated during the course of disease; in cases of gastric ulcers, inflammation of the large intestine, or other serious diseases, it is necessary to consult a doctor.

In line with the principles of Ayurveda, people have three natural forces in them: the creative one – visible when new life appears; the preservative one – preparing for birth; and the transmuting one, which transforms the preservative force into the creative one during birth. It is not possible to change the proportions of *Doshas* with which one was born, yet it is possible to find the equilibrium proper for each of them, and to recognize the dominating *Dosha*, which determines the type of our constitution. Nutrition is an extremely important factor in maintaining internal balance.

Thanks to the knowledge of properties of specific food products and their skilful application, it is possible to preserve or even regain health, or the state of being in harmony with nature – food products have been an integral part of the art of healing for centuries. The sages of Ayurveda assigned basic colours and tastes to each of the *Doshas* and connected them with the physiological and anatomic properties of the organism; with the psyche and spirituality; the manner and style of life; health problems and complaints; and dietary habits [3, 24, 25].

Information about the dietary needs of the organism is provided mainly by the constitution type, related to a given colour and taste of food products:

- ☯ The **Vata** type is connected with a bright yellow/yellow colour. For people of the yellow type, foods rich in carotenoids are advantageous, as are the following tastes: salty, sweet, sour, as well as all spices and herbs, with the exception of raw garlic.
- ☯ The **Pitta** type is correlated with the red colour. For that constitution type, advantageous are the products rich in polyphenols; as well as the following tastes: sweet, bitter, pungent-bitter, as well as all the spices and herbs, with the exception of: sweet basil, bay leaves, marjoram, oregano, rosemary, sage, thyme, bell pepper, and white mustard.
- ☯ The **Kapha** type is associated with a blue-green colour. For that constitution type, cruciferous vegetables, horseradish, radish, and a sharp taste are advantageous.

The current state of knowledge, along with contemporary research methods, enables an unambiguous determination of biologically active substances. Pigments found in plants not only give them their natural colour but, as biologically active phytochemicals, may also help support health and maintain the organism in energy equilibrium. The colour of a specific phytochemical depends on factors related to the habitat of the plant, the pH of its cell sap, the pigment concentration, and the presence of other elements, etc. [4, 9, 10, 14, 15, 26, 27].

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III.1 CAROTENOIDS – THE YELLOW TYPE

Carotenoids are yellow, orange, or red pigments that exhibit lipophilic properties. In plant cells, they are present in chromoplasts. In the organism, they accumulate around cell membranes and internal structures, where they can influence numerous cellular functions and affect the organism's overall health. They must be provided in the diet.

Carotenoids that are hydrocarbons are called carotenes: *α-carotene*, *γ-carotene*, *β-carotene*, *lycopene*; whereas their derivatives containing an oxygen atom in the molecule are called *xanthophylls*, e.g., *zeaxanthin*, *lutein*, and *crocetin*.

The most important structural feature of a carotenoid is the system of conjugated double bonds, which determines the colour, depending on the number of bonds, colours ranging from yellow to red may appear [27, 28, 29, 30].

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A. Carotenoids in Yellow and Yellow-Green Foods

SOURCE: mango, papaya, peach, pumpkin, yellow bell pepper, cucurbit, lemon, orange, tangerine, avocado, savoy, spinach, kiwi, broccoli, Brussels sprouts, green peas.

Pumpkin has a Mexican origin. In its fruit, but first of all in the seeds, there are active substances that have been studied in relation to diseases of the urinary system, prostate gland, chills, while for women, they alleviate the manifestations of menopause with vertigo. Pumpkins are the proverbial bombs, full of vitamins, mineral salts, pectins, and saccharides. The *cucurbitacin* contained in it kills the parasites of the alimentary tract.

Oranges contain therapeutic agents in the peel, pulp, and fruit. The bitter-sweet orange oil extract, called *neroli*, is helpful in depression and anxiety states. Triterpenes, the so-called limonoids, and flavonoids such as naringin, hesperidin, and neohesperidin add bitterness to the fruit. Extracts from raw bitter orange enhance the secretion of gastric juice, make digestion easier and faster, and inhibit the absorption of noxious substances.

Lemons contain anti-cancerous substances, bactericides, and refreshing agents; they enhance the immune system and aid in skin bleaching. Moreover, the aroma of lemon removes sleepiness, aids thinking, and replenishes energy. Lemon juice contains perillyl alcohol. Yellow carotenoids are abundant, with lutein, *zeaxanthin*, and *α-cryptoxanthin* and *β-cryptoxanthin* [29, 31, 32].

Zeaxanthin and lutein are present first of all in the macula lutea. *zeaxanthin* dominates in the central part of the macula, whereas *lutein* is found in its peripheral parts. Yellow pigment absorbs blue light and acts as a filter for ultraviolet radiation, preventing lesions of macula cells. Also, the influence of pigments in the macula has been noted in the reduction of chromatic aberration, thanks to the filtering of the shortwave range of the spectrum.

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Moreover, both *xanthophylls* prevent cataracts and retinal diseases, and protect against age-related diseases, namely age-related macular degeneration and retinal lesions. They also demonstrate a positive influence in conditions of immunological disturbances. Supplementation with lutein increases the density of macular pigments, while lutein found in spinach, broccoli, savoy, and other green vegetables effectively prevents cancers, especially those of the colon. *Zeaxanthin*, *lutein*, and α , and β -cryptoxanthine counteract oxidative lesions of the retina, capture free radicals containing oxygen, and prevent the attacks of free radicals on fatty acids in cell membranes [31, 32, 33].

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B. Carotenoids in Orange Foods

SOURCE: apricot, asparagus, mango, carrot, pumpkin, orange, sweet bell pepper, sweet potatoes

Sweet bell pepper is a rich source of vitamin C. The pungent compound it contains, capsaicin, has analgesic properties and stimulates blood circulation, yet in excess, it may lead to gastritis and enterocolitis. Vitamins P, B₁, and B₂ assist the functioning of the alimentary tract and energy metabolism, help remove LDL cholesterol, and have a beneficial influence on circulation. **Potato** tubers are used in cases of burns/scalding; in inhalations for the upper respiratory tract, they assist in treating the kidneys and ulcers. The routine included in it strengthens blood vessels: solanine and tomatine destroy fungi and harmful bacteria, whereas *leptine* and *demissine* support the nervous system. Potato tubers contain the indispensable amino acids, vitamins, starch, and proteins.

Carrot was used to produce wine as a coffee substitute before its nutritional properties were discovered. Carrots contain alpha- and beta-carotene [26, 28, 29, 34].

Asparagus demonstrates antioxidant properties; it has a rejuvenating effect on the skin and diuretic and purifying actions. It contains vitamin C, coumarin, vanillin, rutin, aromatic oils, and mucus. α , β , γ -carotenes, included in orange foods, undergo transformation to vitamin A, protect cellular membranes against lesions that may be caused by free radicals, prevent the penetration of free radicals into cells, and protect DNA structure [26, 28, 29, 35, 36].

Orange carotenoids may modulate immune system activity and may support cardiovascular health have also been studied in relation to cancer prevention, partly through their role in intercellular communication and, in the case of some xanthophylls, through the possible induction of apoptosis in abnormal cells [26, 28, 29, 34, 35, 36].

β -carotene is an efficient scavenger of oxygen-free radicals and may help protect the skin against oxidative damage. The protective activity of beta-carotene is enhanced by simultaneous supplementation with vitamin E. *Beta-carotene* also assists in the treatment of leukoderma, albinism, and photodermatoses [28, 34, 35, 36, 37].

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C. Carotenoids in Red Foods

SOURCES: fresh and boiled tomatoes, red grapefruit, red sweet and hot bell peppers, oranges, watermelons, papaya, as well as lobster, crab, salmon, and other fish with red flesh. Some 85% of the lycopene available in the diet comes from tomatoes and their processed products.

Tomatoes, besides containing the important health-promoting component – lycopene, also contain vitamin A, highly bioavailable iron, and folic acid, which affect the blood, liver, and skin. The unsaturated fatty acids (UFAs) and pectins may help reduce blood cholesterol levels and are key to preventing atherosclerosis. Due to the substantial content of acids (citric acid, malic acid, nicotinic acid, pantothenic acid, folic acid, oxalic acid), it is used in nutraceuticals [21, 26, 38, 39]. The most crucial phytochemical contained in red foods is *lycopene*. The precursor of *lycopene* is phytoene, synthesized by plants, fungi, and bacteria. Desaturation of phytoene leads to the formation of *lycopene*, which in turn is a precursor /substrate for β -carotene and γ -carotene [27, 29].

Lycopene is a polyunsaturated hydrocarbon without provitamin A activity and is lipid-soluble. It is relatively resistant to photolysis. *Lycopene* accounts for a significant proportion of carotenoids in human serum and is present mainly in the testes, adrenal glands, and prostate gland, and in more modest amounts in adipose tissue, lungs, intestinal walls, and skin. Numerous studies have shown that it is well absorbed and accumulates in tissues, where it may exert biological activity beneficial to human health. [21, 26, 38, 39].

It may help reduce the risk of cancers of the breast, cervix, pancreas, oral cavity, and prostate gland by protecting cellular biomolecules, such as lipids, proteins, lipoproteins, and nucleic acids:

- it stimulates the proliferation of keratinocytes, thus counteracting a reduction in the thickness of the epidermis,
- it controls the differentiation of keratinocytes
- it aids the activity of T lymphocytes and may stimulate the immune system,
- it protects against chronic diseases of the cardiovascular system,
- it reduces the risk of atherosclerosis and its development.

Astaxanthin is a red pigment active in aquatic environments, present in phytoplankton, zooplankton, marine animals, fish (salmon, trout, crabs, shrimp), and some water birds. In water birds, its high concentration is found in the eyes, where it protects the retina from oxidative damage. *Astaxanthin* molecules are small and lipid-soluble; because of their amphipathic properties, they readily capture oxygen free radicals from both sides of the cellular membrane [28, 34, 35, 36].

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It has been found that *astaxanthin*:

- has 10 times stronger influence than other carotenoids upon free radicals
- captures free radicals 100 times more efficiently than vitamin E
- crosses the blood-brain barrier, and in the brain functions as an efficient antioxidant
- is absorbed by eye light-sensitive cells, and protects against photo-oxidation
- the strong anti-neoplastic action of *astaxanthin* is manifested through the blocking of lipid oxidation in cellular membranes and body fluids. It contributes to the reduction of neoplastic cells
- increases the production of *T* cells and antibodies.

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III.2 PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS – RED TYPE

Polyphenols are chemical compounds having more or less complex structures, the common feature of which is the existence of many hydroxyl groups in the ring. From the structural point of view, polyphenols may be divided into several groups [15, 24, 26, 40, 41]:

1. organic acids: derivatives of dihydroxybenzoic acid (e.g., gallic acid, protocatechuic acid) and dihydroxycinnamic acid (e.g., caffeic acid, ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, chlorogenic acid).

Foods that contain phenolic acids are usually yellow/orange, red, violet, or blue in colour.

2. flavan derivatives (e.g., catechin, leucoanthocyanidins) and flavonoids (quercetin, myricetin)
3. stilbene derivatives, including resveratrol, among others
4. products of polymerization of flavan derivatives.

Phenolic compounds [4, 21, 27, 42, 43, 44, 45]:

- ✘ are present in plants in the form of free aglycones or conjugated with sugars as glycosides. Polyphenols are generally water-soluble and assist the carotenoids, soluble in lipids, in protecting all parts of the body. Carotenoids may act as lipid-soluble antioxidants by reducing the activity of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and free radicals, particularly in lipid-rich structures such as cell membranes and lipoproteins - phenolic compounds may scavenge free radicals in aqueous body fluids: blood, lymph, tissue fluids, (cerebro)spinal fluid,
- ✘ chelate toxic inorganic compounds and remove them from the body that way. In herbs, polyphenols have preservative properties, including rosmarinic acid, cinnamic acid, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid, eugenol, and thymol.

Polyphenolic compounds are strong antioxidants and, together with ascorbic acid, tocopherols, and carotenoids, may help protect the organism against oxidative stress.

Polyphenols have a positive effect on the skin. They strengthen the junctions between collagen fibers and participate in collagen formation, with vitamin C indispensable for that process.

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Moreover, polyphenols protect the skin and membranes lining body cavities, as well as other systems – the respiratory and digestive systems, and internal organs containing epithelial tissue [4, 21, 27, 42, 43, 44, 45].

A. Phenol phytochemicals in Red Foods

SOURCES: apples, pears, plums, prunes, pomegranates

Apples contain cellulose, which is valuable for proper digestion; they have been studied for their potential to protect against liver and colon cancer. Their pulp contains numerous valuable acids: malic acid, ellagic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, and coumaric acid. An important flavonoid, quercetin, is found in the skin of red apples [15, 24, 26].

Pomegranates, abundant with phytoestrogens - *estrone* and *estradiol*, assist in maintaining hormonal equilibrium. Phenolic compounds in them may help reduce inflammatory and oxidative processes that affect fatty acids in membranes, thereby helping prevent atherosclerosis [21, 27, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46].

Phenolic acids perform specific functions in the body:

- ✘ *p-coumaric acid, gallic acid* – protection against neoplasms,
- ✘ *cinnamic acid* – antimycotic activity,
- ✘ *ellagic acid* – demonstrates astringent, antimutagenic properties, assists the struggle with carcinomas of the lungs, liver, skin, and oesophagus,
- ✘ *ferulic acid* – anticonvulsive and anti-cancerous effect.

Also, other organic acids cause beneficial changes in the organism [5, 15, 24]:

- ✘ *citric acid* – demonstrates antiseptic properties, prevents the development of gallstones,
- ✘ *malic acid* – has antibacterial and blood-building properties,
- ✘ *vitamin C* is an antioxidant and assists in the synthesis of collagen.

B. Phenolic phytochemicals in Orange Foods

SOURCES: apricots, peaches

Peaches contain essential oils, sugars, pectins, mineral salts, and phenolic acids. They have alkali-forming properties and act as softeners, cleansers, and rejuvenators. The therapeutic properties are also demonstrated by the compresses made of fruit and leaf infusions.

Apricots, fresh as well as dry, contain β -*carotene*, while dried ones contain potassium. Apricot oil has strengthening and beauty-enhancing properties. Peaches and apricots contain *phenolic acids, catechins, flavonoids* [21, 26, 27, 28, 29, 35, 36, 42, 43, 44, 45].

Catechins contained in apricots and peaches, among other things:

- counteract allergic reactions and peptic ulcer diseases,

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- prevent lymphatic cancers, as well as prostate cancer and breast cancer, by blocking, androgenic hormones and estrogen receptors, respectively,
- protect the liver and cells against lesions caused by free radicals, and reduce the risk of heart diseases,
- inhibit the oxidation of plasma lipids through the hydro- and lipophilic properties.

Flavonoids have substantial antioxidant potential; they determine how the organism responds to external stressors and influence the processes of health and beauty. They modify immune function, prevent heart disease, and protect against bacteria and viruses.

Orange phenolic compounds are biologically active substances [21, 27, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47]:

- ✘ *quercetin* – demonstrates a bacteriostatic effect on some bacteria and viruses; causes relaxation of smooth muscles, seals vessel walls, counteracts hypertension, demonstrates antimutagenic and anticarcinogenic activity,
- ✘ *quercetin* and *kaempferol* – have antihistamine and anti-inflammatory effects,
- ✘ *estron* – influences the hormonal equilibrium,
- ✘ *rutin* – prolongs the effect of vitamin C in tissues; it also renders inactive the enzymes, which causes destruction of endothelial capillary vessels.

C. Phenol phytochemicals in Yellow Foods

SOURCES: apples, guava, pear, quince, citrus fruit

Quince is abundant with pectin, iron, vitamin C, potassium, and phosphorus. In the form of tinctures (infusions) and jellies, it has an antibacterial effect against throat and stomach infections. Phenolic acids and flavonoids included in it - *hesperidin*, *quercetin*, *rutin* – improve the condition of blood vessels, have an antioedematous effect, and also *kaempferol*, *quercetin*. Ethereal oils of quince have extremely strong aromatic properties, while the mucus contains the peel's glossy [21, 27, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47].

D. Phenolic phytochemicals in Red and Black Foods

SOURCES: raspberries, blackberries, blueberries, lingonberries, strawberries, cherries

Blueberries are shrubs with violet/blue berries. The berries contain: anthocyanidins - cyanidines delphinidines, mallowidines and others; procyanidins, flavonoids - glycosides, quercetin derivatives, and kaempferol, as well as organic acids - malic acid, citric acid, quinic acid, and vitamins from the B group and vitamin C [9, 14, 21, 27, 32, 42, 43, 44, 45].

Cyanidin and *malvidin* seal blood vessels and aid in the treatment of disturbances of microcirculation in the eyeball. Blueberry fruit is used in cases of disease of the organ of sight - diabetic retinopathies, cataract, inflammatory conditions, and others. Also, they demonstrate astringent, antithrombotic, and anti-inflammatory properties [21, 27, 31, 32, 42, 43, 44, 45].

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Cherry fruit contains substantial amounts of copper and iron, stimulates appetite, and adds vitamins to the diet. Cherry tincture is used to fight colds and digestive problems. [5, 15].

Anthocyanidins can be found in all berry fruits, in cherries, raspberries, strawberries, lingonberries, cowberries, quince, pear, plum, and green tea. Those biologically active pigments are water-soluble; they give fruits and flowers their red, blue, or violet colour. Their colour depends on the environmental pH, the presence of other pigments, such as flavonoids and carotenoids, and the presence of metals. In an acidic environment, they are usually red, whereas in a basic environment, they are blue [9, 14, 21, 27, 32, 42, 43].

Specific side chains determine the final chemical structure, leading to the division into anthocyanins, anthocyanidins, and proanthocyanidins. They reveal a series of biological properties [21, 27, 31, 32, 42, 43, 44, 45]:

- have antioxidant action;
- improve blood supply in the area of the iris;
- accelerate the regeneration of rhodopsin;
- are used in the treatment of brittleness of capillary vessels, in microangiopathies, and in the therapy of peripheral vessels.

E. Phenolic phytochemicals in Red and Violet Foods

SOURCES: grapes, blackberries, rhubarb

Grapes are used for winemaking. The color of grape wines, their taste, and aroma depend on the presence of anthocyanins, flavonoids (quercetin, myricetin, kaempferol, and their glycosides), and catechins (epicatechin, epigallocatechin, and others). In grape wines, a polyphenol has been identified – *resveratrol*. The dark grape fruits contain: sugars, dietary fiber, pectin, vitamins C, B₁, B₂, B₆, B₁₂, P, PP, folic acid, salts of chromium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, selenium, iron, manganese, cobalt, as well as numerous enzymes, while their skin contains antioxidants and a glycoside – *enin*. Extract from grape stones is a natural antidepressant; it alleviates the symptoms of senile dementia. Oil extracted from grape seed is incorporated into natural epidermal ceramides and, together with them, seals the epidermal barrier. Grape seeds contain bioflavonoids, and when taken with vitamin C, they help prevent collagen damage and reduce arthritis symptoms [15, 24, 44].

Preparations from the vine reduce osmotic blood pressure; they diminish the permeability of vascular walls. They alleviate the symptoms of venous-lymphatic insufficiency and increase lymph flow [15, 24, 25, 44].

Resveratrol contained in grape seeds exerts an exceptionally beneficial influence upon the cardiovascular system; it prevents lesions of arterial walls; it counteracts platelet aggregation; it reduces lipid levels; it inhibits proliferation of cancerous cells; it also alleviates the complaints related to menopause [40, 41, 49].

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F. Phenol phytochemicals in Green Foods

SOURCES: green and black tea

Green tea is not subject to fermentation processes. Only leaves are the medicinal raw material. Their infusion contains tannins, caffeine, vitamins C, B, and K, bioflavonoids, and mineral salts. Young leaves of green tea are particularly abundant with the so-called free catechins - gallic acid, epicatechin, epigallocatechin, catechin, and contain a group of catechins, which contain gallic acid in their structure – gallates: gallic acid, epigallocatechins, epicatechins, epigallocatechins. All the phenolic compounds in green tea contribute to its bitter-acrid taste and pale yellow colour. The process of fermentation changes the quality composition of the tea leaves, as due to their oxidation, catechins are transformed into new compounds – theaflavins and thearubigins. In fact, theaflavins impart the orange–red colour to black tea infusions [18, 22, 36, 48, 50, 52]:

Green tea is used for prophylactic reasons, and in the treatment of systemic diseases

- reduces the risk of myocardial infarction, assists the immunological functions,
- neutralizes free radicals; inhibits the development of bacterial infections, viral infections, and mycotic infections,
- controls the level of cholesterol,
- maintains the required level of mineral components in bones - fluorine, potassium, calcium, magnesium, zinc, copper, and cobalt,
- reduces allergic reactions.

III.3 CRUCIFEROUS PLANTS – GREEN TYPE

SOURCES:

A – cruciferous vegetables: broccoli, cabbage, cauliflower, brussels sprouts, turnip, kale, watercress

B – mustard plants: black mustard (seeds), rapeseed, horseradish, radish, watercress

The medicinal properties of those foods are related to their main components - vitamin C, provitamin A, sulfur-containing compounds, which exert a beneficial influence on the skin, potassium, which participates in nervous system reactions, anti-ulcer components, as well as phytoncides that have an antibacterial effect. Compresses from cabbage leaves are astringent for wounds; they alleviate rheumatic conditions and rheumatic arthritis of the knee joints. Sauerkraut demonstrates antiputrefactive action and is beneficial for the digestive tract; sauerkraut juice is a medicine for chronic constipation [19, 20, 35].

Cabbage and broccoli most evidently protect the organism against carcinoma of the urinary bladder, which is associated with a substantial content of glucosinolates, products of biochemical transformations induced by crushing, chopping, and boiling. Calcium D-*glucarate* prevents the development of lung carcinoma and other neoplastic processes in various tissues

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throughout the body. Broccoli, cabbage, and brussels sprouts contain *indole compounds*, a phytochemical, which, similar to calcium *D-glucarate* inhibits the development of estrogen-dependent breast carcinoma.

Cruciferous plants constitute a group of products with bitter and spicy taste and a characteristic strong smell. The strong smell intensifies during chopping and boiling, as the enzyme myrosinase, present in those foods, begins to decompose compounds containing sulfur, among which the most important are glucoraphanin and glucobrassicin. Sulfur compounds efficiently transform toxins and other noxious chemical compounds, which find their way to the organism, or are produced in our tissues. Similarly, sulfur-containing enzymes transform toxins from the external environment, drugs, and compounds present in food and drinks [6, 19, 20, 53]. Mustard has been used for centuries to treat nerves, bones, and rheumatic diseases, as well as oedemas, contusions, and bruises. Research has demonstrated that its top contains indoles, which inhibit estrogen activity and help counter neoplastic diseases. Moreover, white mustard is useful in treating neoplasms, heart disease, and anemia. It contains active phytochemicals, isothiocyanates, which prevent carcinoma of the lungs, esophagus, stomach, and colon; they also lead to the self-destruction of neoplastic cells [6, 19, 20, 53].

Compounds containing sulfur are also found in garlic and plants allied to it. The enzyme called alliinase, in the course of crushing, chopping, or cooking, transforms the unique hydrocarbon-sulfur bonds present in garlic into biologically active phytochemicals—thiosulfonates – ajoene, *S-allylmercaptocysteine*.

Garlic contains vitamins C, B2, B1, and PP, as well as mineral salts such as calcium, phosphorus, manganese, chlorine, and iodine. It also contains phytoncides, which are substances with strong disinfectant properties. Garlic stimulates the digestive system, increases the secretion of gastric juice, and may have beneficial effects in liver and gallbladder diseases, as well as in hypertension. It may also help protect blood vessels against age-related changes.

When garlic is crushed, the enzyme alliinase converts alliin into allicin, a sulfur-containing compound associated with antimicrobial activity. If garlic is deprived of its aromatic allicin, it loses a significant part of its valuable properties. What is more, the phytochemicals contained in it reduce the level of cholesterol and blood pressure, prevent the sticking of platelets, and reveal anti-neoplastic properties [6, 11, 18, 19, 20].

Photo source: www.young4softmatter.pl

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IV. SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

Nutrition provides organisms with nutrients that allow them to maintain mental and physical well-being, slow aging, and support overall health. However, not all the food products we consume benefit our bodies. That is why research in nutrition aims to identify, in addition to nutrients, other substances in food that are valuable for their health-promoting and preventive properties [5, 15, 18, 20]

The plant-based foods available on the market, labeled as functional foods, are assumed to have a prophylactic or health-promoting influence on the human organism [54]. In addition, such food provides basic nutrients, has sensory properties, and participates in the regulation of important physiological processes in the organism. Among the substances that have a beneficial influence upon the organism, the following are listed: cellulose, oligosaccharides, amino acids, peptides, proteins, vitamins, choline, lecithin, polyunsaturated fatty acids, mineral components, as well as phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and other phytochemicals [4, 18, 19, 24, 42, 44].

In light of the above facts, the groups of yellow, red, and green products discussed in the study meet the criteria for functional foods. They provide the organism with essential nutrients, help regulate metabolic processes, have health-promoting and preventive properties, and contain phytochemicals; moreover, such a diet can be tailored to each individual's *Dosha*. Thus, the phytochemicals present in food not only add colour to it, but also have a beneficial effect upon the organism [9, 14, 15, 26, 27].

The colour of food may be interpreted as a point of contact between Ayurvedic and modern nutritional assessment. In Ayurveda, food is not evaluated only in terms of its nutritive value, but also through its sensory qualities and its effects on the body and mind. Classical Ayurvedic dietetics describes food in terms of categories such as taste (*Rasa*), qualities (*Guna*), potency or energetic effect (*Virya*), post-digestive effect (*Vipaka*), and influence on the balance of the *Doshas*. Ayurvedic literature also refers to sensory characteristics such as colour or appearance (*Varna/Rupa*), smell (*Gandha*), taste (*Rasa*), and touch or texture (*Sparsha*) as elements involved in the perception and evaluation of food [3, 25, 55].

From this perspective, colour should not be treated as an independent or sufficient criterion for food selection in Ayurveda. Rather, it may be understood as one visible aspect of a broader assessment of food quality, which also includes the individual constitution (*Prakriti*), current imbalance (*Vikriti*), season, digestive capacity, and the manner in which food is prepared and consumed. Thus, colour can function as a supportive sensory signal, but not as the only basis for dietary choice [3, 24, 25].

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It is worth stressing that recent scientific findings provide clear support for the Ayurvedic principle that the colour of food is an important factor in human health and dietary evaluation³:

“The color of food plays a crucial role in consumers’ food selection, serving as one of the most important cues perceived before tasting”

Contemporary studies do not directly confirm Ayurvedic colour classifications in a biomedical sense; however, they show that food colour is associated with specific bioactive compounds and may influence sensory perception, taste expectations, food attractiveness, and the perceived health value of food [9, 10, 11, 56, 57]. In this sense, Ayurvedic attention to food colour can be interpreted as consistent with a broader, holistic understanding of nutrition, in which visual, sensory, biochemical, and individual factors jointly contribute to dietary choice and health-oriented eating patterns.

Modern nutritional science provides an additional explanation for the importance of food colour. The colour of food may be understood as a useful link between traditional Ayurvedic sensory assessment and contemporary nutritional science. From both perspectives, colour should be considered an element of a broader dietary assessment rather than a stand-alone rule. In this sense, modern nutrition and food technology may complement the Ayurvedic view that food is a key element in maintaining health, balance, and quality of life [30, 35, 50, 51].

High-pressure processing (HPP) is particularly relevant for colourful fruit and vegetable products because non-thermal processing may help preserve pigments responsible for colour, including carotenoids, chlorophylls, and anthocyanins, while also supporting the maintenance of sensory and nutritional quality. This is important because the colour of plant-based foods is closely related to the presence of bioactive compounds and may therefore serve as a visible indicator of their potential health-promoting value [38, 56, 57].

³ Shu, Y., Gao, H., Wang, Y., & Wei, Y. (2025). Food emotional perception and eating willingness under different lighting colors: A preliminary study based on consumer facial expression analysis. *Foods*, 14(19), Article 3440, p.2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14193440>

Photo source: pexels.com

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